

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF ORGANIC FERTILIZERS AND GROWTH PROMOTERS ON POTATO GROWTH, DEVELOPMENT AND TUBERING

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Abstract

The article presents the results of field experimental studies of changes in growth, development, phenological stages, intensity of tuber accumulation and yield under the influence of different timings of application of biohumus, supercompost and growth stimulants, bioliquid and free fulvic acid.

The study's findings showed that a fractional application of biohumus and supercompost (via seeding and via nutrition) to potato crops grown on the soils of the river valleys of the Sevan basin has a more beneficial effect on their growth, development, and accumulation of tubers than a single application of these quantities (via seeding).

During the fertilizing potato fields, it is necessary to apply biohumus to the soil at the rate of 8 t/ha or 10 t/ha of supercompost (60% through sowing, 40% through nutrition in the bud formation phase) and during the growing season, apply external-root feeding by bioliquid (in the bud formation and flowering phases). As a result, the high-quality potato crop will be provided (390-400 c/ha), which in its turn will contribute to the improvement of the ecological conditions of Lake Sevan.

Keywords: Biohumus - supercompost - potatoes - growth stimulants - growth and development – tubering intensity

Introduction

Sevan is the only Transcaucasian large lake, which serves as a perspective reservoir for the strategic reserves of drinking water for Armenia and neighboring countries. The basin of Sevan, being one of the most extensive agricultural zones of the republic, differs somewhat from other agricultural regions in terms of its physical and geographical characteristics, geological structure, climate, soil, water, and vegetation aspects.

Sevan ecological state is mainly due to industrial and domestic wastewaters, livestock wastes pollution, as well as the occurrence of biogenic elements upon the leaching of mineral fertilizers and pesticides from the soil mass of agroecosystems related to erosion processes (Galstyan M.H. 2007, Galstyan M.H. 2018).

Upon the investigations it has been found out that 269 tons of nitrate, 144 tons of nitrite, 105 tons of oil product, 58 tons of phosphate and 2837 tons of fecal matters are annually dumped into Sevan Lake which are serious threats for the regular growth and development of fauna and flora of the lake at the same time causing biogenic contamination (eutrophication) in the lake (Movsisyan V.M. 2002).

Low rainfall in the basin, especially during the vegetation period, low content of organic matter in the soil, accumulated due to the influence of high air temperature and systemic winds plant residues, quickly mineralize and a small amount of humus accumulates in the soil. In such conditions, without the application

of scientifically based technologies in the soil, provision of optimal reserves of nutrients and moisture, it is not possible to ensure a high and quality harvest from cultivated crops, especially potatoes, even with very good agrotechnics. In addition, it is impossible to simultaneously contribute to the improvement of the ecological condition of the waters of Lake Sevan, its fauna, and to ensure normal functioning of flora (Galstyan M.H. 2007, Galstyan M.H. et al 2020).

Therefore, the systemic and complex solution of the indicated problems is extremely important and relevant and follows from the requirements of the strategy of environmental protection and agriculture of the region, as well as priorities of ensuring food safety.

Material and methods

The main condition for the growth, development and increase of potato productivity, improvement of quality indicators, as well as reduction of cost is the provision of maximum productivity per unit area. While solving these problems the conditions of a healthy lifestyle should be taken into account. Along with many factors (the introduction of new high-yielding varieties, the use of effective methods of pest and disease control, the improvement of production and sales methods), the use of scientifically based fertilizers and growth stimulators, which provide high-yield at low costs, is of particular importance in terms of enhancing and protecting the environment.

Literature data clearly show that with intensive technologies to obtain high and stable yields of agricultural crops, including potatoes, a large amount of mineral fertilizers and other chemicals is used, which is confirmed by the studies of many domestic and foreign scientists (Galstyan M.H. 2003, Mineev V.G. 2004, Yagodin B.A. et al 1987). In this sense, the use of an alternative way of growing crops is of paramount importance.

Considering the importance of the problem, the task was set to study the effect of the amounts and methods of applying organic fertilizers (biohumus, supercompost) and growth stimulants (free fulvic acid, bioliquid) obtained by the latest methods on plant growth, development, tuber accumulation and the amount of the crop obtained in the lake hollows.

During the growing season, phenological observations, biometric measurements were carried out and the changes caused by the action of one or another soil improver on aboveground and underground organs, the accumulation of potato tubers and the amount of the crop obtained were calculated in order to implement the best option in agricultural production.

The field experiments were set up in the fluvial-terrace soils (Artsvanist community of Gegharkunik region) characteristic to the Sevan basin; here the prevailing part of potato plantations (82.0 %) is cultivated in the mentioned soils, while 18.0 % is cultivated in the leached black soils. [3]. The reaction (pH) of the soils of the experimental field ranges from 6.7-7.0, the amount of cations (Ca^{++} , Mg^{++}) absorbed by the soil layer is 25.3-30.3 mg/eq per 100 g of soil. The content of humus is 4.2%, easily hydrolysable nitrogen is weak (3.6 mg), mobile phosphorus is moderate (5.4 mg), exchangeable potassium is good (37.0 mg per 100 g of soil).

Field experiments were carried out in triplicate, the area of each variant in repetition was 30 m² with the following options:

1. Control (without fertilization),
2. Biohumus: 8 t/ha (via seeding) + bioliquid: 2 sprays,
3. Biohumus: 5 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha (via nutrition) + bioliquid: 2 sprays,
4. Biohumus: 5 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha (via nutrition) + fulvic acid: 2 sprays,
5. Supercompost: 10 t/ha (via seeding) + bioliquid: 2 sprays,
6. Supercompost: 6 t/ha (via seeding) + 4 t/ha (via nutrition) + bioliquid: 2 sprays,
7. Supercompost: 6 t/ha (via seeding) + 4 t/ha (via nutrition) + fulvic acid: 2 sprays.

The potato planting rate was 37.0 c/ha, further processing and harvesting was carried out in accordance with the agricultural rules adopted in the region. In one case, the full rate of equivalent amounts of biohumus and supercompost was given at a time, from seeds (options 2 and 5), and in other cases, fractionally, from seeds and with nutrition at the cocooning stage, as indicated on the diagram. Based on the nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium contents in the supercompost and biohumus available in these fertilizers the appropriate rates have been estimated, the content of NPK in supercompost and biohumus has made 1.56 and 2.3 % (N), 1.3 and 2.4 % (P_2O_5), 1.6 and 2.0 % (K_2O) respectively.

In the variants of the application of these organic fertilizers, a double spraying (extra root method) was also carried out with a growth-stimulating bioliquid or fulvic acid at the rate of 3 l/ha during the periods of bud formation and flowering. The agrochemical indicators of soils were determined by the universal methods given in the methodological manual for agrochemical analyzes published by B.A. Yagodin (Yagodin B.A. et al 1989), yield data were subjected to mathematical analysis, experimental error (S_x , %) and determination of the least significant difference ($\text{LSD}_{0.95, c}$) through the method of analysis of variance (Dospechov B.A. 1973).

Results and discussion

According to the average data of the replicates of the field experiment, equivalent quantities of biohumus and supercompost and different terms of application, as well as growth stimulants bioliquid and fulvic acid, had a certain effect on the germination, growth and development of potatoes. Compared to the non-fertilizing (control) variant, both single and fractional application of biohumus and supercompost led to an acceleration of the germination of potato seedlings by an average of 3 (in the case of supercompost) and 5 days (in the case of biohumus) in all variants of the study. If in the variant without fertilization, potato tubers (planting material) germinated after 32-33 days, then in the variants with supercompost production - after 29-30 days, and in the variants with biohumus after 27-28 days.

The effect of biohumus and growth promoters is more obvious during the transition of potato phenological stages. If this effect is insignificant at the initial stages, then at the final stages (flowering and maturation) the effect of biohumus, bioliquid and fulvic acid is obvious: compared to the variants of application of supercompost and the same growth stimulants, the duration of vegetation of plants has decreased somewhat.

In other words, if it took potato plants 93-96 days from germination to maturity in the experimental version, 87-91 days in the supercompost and growth stimulator versions, then 83-86 days in the versions of both one-time and small applications of biohumus and growth stimulators, or the duration of vegetation was shortened by 10 days compared to the control and by 4-5 days compared to the equivalent options of applying supercompost and growth stimulators (Tab. 1).

So if it took 93-96 days for potato plants to grow from germination to maturity in the test version, 87-91 days for plants treated with supercompost and growth stimulators, and 83-86 days for plants treated with both one-time and fractional applications of biohumus and growth stimulants, respectively, the duration of vegetation was shortened by 10 days compared to the control and by 4-5 days compared to the equivalent options of using supercompost and growth promoters (Tab. 1).

This circumstance is also important in the sense that households will get the opportunity to collect and store the potato crop without losses, as during potato harvesting in the mountainous regions of the republic, including the Sevan basin, there are frequent rains and wet snow.

In the course of the studies, it was revealed that in the versions of the one-time and fractional application of biohumus and supercompost, as well as bioliquid and fulvic acid, the plants grew more lushly compared

to the control, had a dark green color, greater branching of the stems and provided a dense leaf mass.

If in the variants of a single application of equivalent doses of biohumus and supercompost, the height of the plants increased by 11.0 and 7.4 cm, the number of stems by 2.6 and 3.4 cm, respectively, compared with

the control, then in the variants that received the same doses, when carried out with growth stimulants, plant height increased by 4.1-4.3 cm with fractional application of biohumus and by 3.4-3.7 cm with the use of supercompost and growth stimulants (Tab. 1).

Table 1
Effect of organic fertilizers and growth promoters on potato phenological phase transition, above ground mass and stolons (average data 2020-2022)

Number of stolons/pcs	10,5 ± 0,2	16,8 ± 0,4	17,5 ± 0,3	17,2 ± 0,3	15,2 ± 0,2	16,4 ± 0,4	16,7 ± 0,3
Weight	72 ± 3	160 ± 4	185 ± 4	170 ± 5	170 ± 3	162 ± 6	164 ± 5
g/crop	200 ± 5	340 ± 8	375 ± 5	368 ± 4	345 ± 6	369 ± 3	371 ± 4
Number of stems	3,5 ± 0,9	6,1 ± 0,2	7,8 ± 0,3	7,6 ± 0,3	6,0 ± 0,5	6,9 ± 0,3	7,2 ± 0,4
Height of crops (average data)	45,2	56,2	58,0	57,3	52,6	54,0	53,4
Extinction of tops (average data)	96	83	85	86	87	91	90
From seedling (day)	59	51	52	54	54	57	55
Bud formation (average data)	39	37	36	35	37	38	37
The emergence of seedlings to the surface (finish, average data)	6/06	1/06	1/06	30/05	3/06	3/06	3/06
1.	Control (without fertilization)	Biohumus: 8 t/ha (via seeding) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Biohumus: 5 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha (via nutrition) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Biohumus: 5 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha (via nutrition) + fulvic acid: 2 sprays	Supercompost: 10 t/ha (via seeding) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Supercompost: 6 t/ha (via seeding) + 4 t/ha (via nutrition) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Supercompost: 6 t/ha (via seeding) + 4 t/ha (via nutrition) + fulvic acid: 2 sprays
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6.							
7.							
N							

From the data of the same table it can be seen that similar changes were observed in the weight mass of stems and leaves and the number of stolons. Everywhere, compared with the unfertilized variant, the mass of stems increased by 140-171 grams, leaves by 88-98 grams, and the number of stolons by 4.7-7 in the variants that received organic fertilizers and growth stimulants. At the same time, the research results showed that

the fractional application of equivalent doses of biohumus and supercompost had a more favorable effect on the above growth indicators, the development of potatoes, aboveground and underground organs, as a result of which, providing better conditions for the accumulation of potato tubers and increasing the number of crops compared to with a single application (Tab. 2).

In the course of research, comparing the effect of bioliquid and fulvic acid growth stimulants on the growth, development and accumulation of potato tubers, it is clearly seen that bioliquid, both biohumus and supercompost, had a more beneficial effect than fulvic acid in equivalent doses. If the increase in potato yield was 202.0 c/ha and 199.0 c/ha or 102.0 and 100.5% on the background of biohumus and supercompost, under the influence of radical nutrition with bioliquid, compared with the control, then on the background of the same fertilizers, the increase in yield in the variants, the use of fulvic acid was 166.0 c/ha (83.8%) and 189.0 c/ha (95.5%), respectively. As a result of one-time application of biohumus and supercompost, if the average

rate of tuber accumulation per day from bud formation to maturity was 9.1 and 8.7 grams, respectively, then in fractional applications of the same doses, it was 10.5 and 9.8 grams.

As can be seen from the data in the table, in the variants of a single and fractional application of biohumus, compared with similar doses and terms of applying supercompost, the stimulating effect of biohumus on the formation of stolons and potato tubers, as well as the intensity of tuber accumulation was revealed, which undoubtedly contributed to an increase in yield (Tab. 2).

Table 2
Effect of organic fertilizers and growth promoters, by phenological phases on tuber and average yield (2020-2022)

Additional yield	%	c/ha (2020-2022)	Phenological phases							LSD _{0,95} , c				
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7					
Average yield, c/ha	198,0 ± 3,0	328,0 ± 4,0	400,0 ± 6,0	364,0 ± 4,5	342,0 ± 5,0	397,0 ± 5,6	387,0 ± 4,8	189,0	7,4					
From bud formation to extinction of tops	6,2	9,1	10,5	10,2	8,7	9,8	9,6							
Weight of tubers by development stage, g	57	46	49	51	50	53	53							
Variants	Control (without fertilization)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-					
										102,0	83,8	72,7	100,5	95,5
										202,0	166,0	144,0	199,0	189,0
										400,0 ± 6,0	364,0 ± 4,5	342,0 ± 5,0	397,0 ± 5,6	387,0 ± 4,8
										10,5	10,2	8,7	9,8	9,6
										49	51	50	53	53
										487,9 ± 4,5	590,1 ± 4,5	505,1 ± 4,5	590,9 ± 5,45	578,6 ± 6,0
325,0 ± 5,0	339,0 ± 4,0	349,0 ± 3,5	338,0 ± 5,0	340,0 ± 5,5										
69,3 ± 6,0	69,9 ± 3,5	71,4 ± 5,5	69,9 ± 3,5	70,6 ± 2,5	71,5 ± 3,0	69,8 ± 5,5								
Control (without fertilization)	Biohumus: 8 t/ha (via seeding) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Biohumus: 5 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha (via nutrition) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Biohumus: 5 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha (via nutrition) + fulvic acid: 2 sprays	Biohumus: 5 t/ha (via seeding) + 3 t/ha (via nutrition) + fulvic acid: 2 sprays	Supercompost: 10 t/ha (via seeding) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Supercompost: 6 t/ha (via seeding) + 4 t/ha (via nutrition) + bioliquid: 2 sprays	Supercompost: 6 t/ha (via seeding) + 4 t/ha (via nutrition) + fulvic acid: 2 sprays	7.						
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.								

Thus, the fractional application of equivalent amounts of biohumus and supercompost (via seeding and via nutrition) to potato seedlings grown on the soils of the river valleys of the Sevan basin, has a more beneficial effect on the growth, development of potatoes, the intensity of tuber accumulation and the yield, than a single application of these fertilizers (via seeding).

Compared to equal dosages of biohumus and supercompost the rate of 6 l/ha of growth-stimulating bioliquid with foliar nutrition produced a larger yield increase (10.0-37.0 q) than the same rate of free fulvic acid.

When feeding potato crops cultivated in the high-mountain zone, it is necessary to add biohumus to the soil at the rate of 8 t/ha or 10 t/ha of supercompost (60% of sowing, 40% of nutrition in the bud formation phase). and during the growing season, at the stage of cocooning and flowering: foliar top dressing with growth-stimulating bioliquid at the rate of 3 l/ha.

The use of this technology will increase the yield of potatoes, as well as improve the ecological state of Lake Sevan and its environment.

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